

MLOPS INFRASTRUCTURE AND DEVELOPMENT FOR LHCb MONITORING OPTIMIZATION

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

The LHCb experiment operates thousands of servers using advanced monitoring systems in an on-premise cloud environment. To enhance observability and streamline operations, this project implements a cloud-based MLOps infrastructure tailored to the LHCb environment. It includes workflows and pipelines for seamless model deployment and management, interfaces for efficient interaction, and tools to monitor and evaluate model performance. This robust setup enables the integration of advanced machine learning techniques to further enhance the LHCb monitoring system.

ABSTRACT

The LHCb experiment generates and processes vast amounts of monitoring data to ensure the reliable operation of its large-scale distributed computing infrastructure. Managing this complexity requires not only advanced monitoring tools but also a flexible machine learning platform that integrates securely into the existing on-premise cloud environment. This project introduces a Kubeflow-based MLOps infrastructure adapted to these constraints. Deployment was carried out in a private network environment, necessitating custom authentication through LDAP integration with Dex, and namespace-aware access control achieved via ClusterRoleBindings and role-assignment scripts. GPU resources, critical for training efficiency, were optimized through time-slicing techniques. Administrative visibility across namespaces was additionally implemented to align Kubernetes-level permissions with the Kubeflow user interface. The resulting infrastructure establishes a secure, scalable, and resource-efficient platform for machine learning workflows at LHCb.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The LHCb experiment at CERN operates one of the largest distributed computing infrastructures in high-energy physics. Thousands of servers are continuously monitored to ensure the reliable processing of data generated by the detector. This monitoring system produces vast amounts of information, which is essential for detecting anomalies, optimizing resource usage, and maintaining operational stability. As the scale and complexity of the infrastructure increase, traditional monitoring approaches face limitations in terms of automation, adaptability, and the integration of advanced analysis techniques.

Machine learning offers promising opportunities to enhance monitoring by enabling intelligent anomaly detection, predictive maintenance, and optimization of system parameters. However, developing and deploying machine learning solutions in such an environment introduces challenges of scalability, reproducibility, and integration with existing infrastructure. These challenges are further amplified by the constraints of the LHCb computing environment, which is based on an on-premise cloud and operates in a private network with strict security and access requirements.

To address these needs, this project focuses on the design and implementation of a tailored MLOps infrastructure that enables machine learning workflows to be developed, deployed, and managed within the LHCb environment. The objective is to create a secure and scalable platform that provides researchers and engineers with the necessary tools to integrate machine learning models into the monitoring pipeline, while respecting the operational constraints of the computing infrastructure. The chosen framework for this task is Kubeflow [1], an open-source machine learning platform designed to run on Kubernetes, which offers the modularity and flexibility required to adapt to the specific requirements of LHCb.

2 KUBEFLOW

Kubeflow is an open-source platform designed to simplify the development, orchestration, deployment, and management of machine learning workflows on Kubernetes. Its primary objective is to provide a scalable and reproducible framework that integrates the various stages of the machine learning lifecycle into a single environment. By leveraging Kubernetes as its foundation, Kubeflow inherits strong capabilities for container orchestration, multi-user isolation, and resource scheduling, making it well-suited for large-scale scientific and enterprise environments.

The platform is modular, offering a set of components that can be deployed independently or combined to build end-to-end machine learning pipelines. Among its most relevant components are:

- **Central Dashboard:** A unified web interface that integrates these components and facilitates user access.

Figure 1: Central Dashboard

- **Notebooks:** Interactive development environments (e.g., Jupyter) for data exploration and prototyping.

Figure 2: Inside a notebook server

- Pipelines: A system for defining, executing, and managing machine learning workflows in a reproducible manner.

Figure 3: Example pipeline

- Serving (KFServing/KServe): Tools for deploying trained models as scalable, production-ready services.

The screenshot shows the 'flowers' service overview with the following details:

- Status: Ready
- URL external: http://flowers.kubeflow-user.example.com
- URL internal: http://flowers.kubeflow-user.svc.cluster.local/v1/models/flowers:predict
- Component: predictor
- Storage URI: gs://kfserving-samples/models/tensorflow/flowers
- Runtime: Tensorflow 1.14.0
- Protocol Version: (empty)

InferenceService Conditions:

Status	Type	Last Transition Time	Reason	Message
✓	IngressReady	23 minutes ago		
✓	PredictorConfigurationReady	23 minutes ago		

Figure 4: Example for model serving

- Katib: A framework for hyperparameter optimization and automated experimentation.

Figure 5: Example result of a Katib experiment

In the context of LHCb, Kubeflow provides a flexible foundation to integrate machine learning into existing monitoring workflows. Its native support for multi-user environments and GPU-accelerated workloads aligns well with the requirements of a large scientific collaboration. Furthermore, the ability to adapt authentication, authorization, and resource management mechanisms makes Kubeflow a promising choice for deployment in a private, security-restricted infrastructure. [1]

3 IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 DEPLOYMENT IN A PRIVATE NETWORK

Deploying Kubeflow in the experiment's computing environment required addressing the restrictions imposed by operating within a private network. Standard Kubeflow installation procedures rely on internet connectivity to retrieve container images, manifests, and Helm charts from public repositories. In an air-gapped or firewall-restricted environment, this direct access is not possible, and therefore an alternative approach was necessary.

To enable installation, all the necessary container images were accessed via the internal registry, registry.cern.ch, which is accessible from within the network. Similarly, manifests [2] were downloaded using proxies and stored locally. Installation scripts and configuration files were adapted to reference these internal resources instead of their original external sources. This ensured that every component of Kubeflow could be deployed and maintained without relying on external connectivity.

Additional adjustments were necessary to accommodate components that attempted to perform external calls during initialization. These were configured to rely exclusively on internal endpoints, ensuring stability and independence from external networks. Through these measures, a fully functional Kubeflow deployment was achieved in an isolated environment, forming the foundation for further customization.

3.2 AUTHENTICATION AND AUTHORIZATION

Secure multi-user access was a fundamental requirement for integrating Kubeflow into the LHCb environment. The platform relies on Dex as its identity provider, which by default supports external authentication systems such as GitHub, Google, or static user accounts. These options were unsuitable in a restricted on-premise environment where user authentication must be performed against internal services.

To address this, Dex was configured to integrate with the Lightweight Directory Access Protocol (LDAP), the directory service already in use for user management within the infrastructure. LDAP provides a centralized mechanism for storing user credentials, group memberships, and associated attributes in a hierarchical structure, enabling consistent authentication across services.

The configuration involved defining Dex's LDAP connector to bind securely to the internal LDAP server using encrypted communication. User attributes such as email and unique identifiers were mapped to Dex claims, ensuring that authenticated users could be properly recognized by Kubeflow. The LDAP integration can be reproduced by adding the following connector definition to Dex's ConfigMap:

```
1 connectors:
2 - type: ldap
3   id: ldap
4   name: LDAP
5   config:
6     host: <host_ip_address>
7     insecureNoSSL: false
8     insecureSkipVerify: true
9     usernamePrompt: "LHCb username"
10    userSearch:
```



```

11     baseDN: OU=lhcb,DC=lbdaq,DC=cern,DC=ch
12     filter:
13     ↪ "(memberOf=CN=onliners,OU=Groups,OU=lhcb,DC=lbdaq,DC=cern,DC=ch)"
14     username: sAMAccountName
15     idAttr: sAMAccountName
16     emailAttr: userPrincipalName
17     nameAttr: displayName
18 groupSearch:
19     baseDN: OU=Groups,OU=lhcb,DC=lbdaq,DC=cern,DC=ch
20     filter: "(objectClass=groupOfMembers)"
21     userAttr: DN
22     groupAttr: member
23     nameAttr: cn

```

In addition to standard user authentication, an administrative account was provisioned to allow privileged management of the system. A static user named admin was created within Dex, and a ClusterRoleBinding was defined to grant this user full access across all namespaces. To ensure that the Kubeflow user interface reflected this level of access, a custom script was implemented to assign the admin user contributor permissions in every namespace. This alignment between Kubernetes-level privileges and the Kubeflow UI resolved inconsistencies and provided the administrator with complete visibility and control. A simplified version of the script is shown below:

```

1 for ns in $(kubectl get ns -o jsonpath='{.items[*].metadata.name}'); do
2     kubectl create rolebinding "$RB_NAME" \
3         --clusterrole=kubeflow-edit \
4         --user="$ADMIN_EMAIL" \
5         -n "$ns" \
6         --dry-run=client -o yaml | \
7         kubectl apply -f -
8 done

```

Through these measures, a secure and role-aware authentication system was established, enabling both regular users and administrators to access Kubeflow reliably within the LHCb environment.

3.3 GPU RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Efficient utilization of GPU resources was another key requirement for adapting Kubeflow to the LHCb environment. By default, Kubernetes schedules GPUs as indivisible devices, assigning an entire GPU to a single pod. This approach leads to significant underutilization when workloads do not fully exploit the available resources, particularly in interactive or lightweight tasks common during model development.

One potential solution is Multi-Instance GPU (MIG) [3], a technology available on NVIDIA A100 and similar GPUs, which allows physical GPUs to be partitioned into smaller, isolated instances. Each instance operates as an independent GPU device, enabling multiple workloads to share the same physical card with strong isolation guarantees. However, the GPUs available for this project do not support MIG, making this option infeasible in the current setup.

Instead, GPU sharing was enabled using time-slicing. With this method, a GPU is divided temporally rather than physically, allowing multiple pods to access the device in short, alternating time slices. The scheduling frequency is sufficiently high to provide users with the experience of near-simultaneous GPU usage, while maintaining fairness between workloads. The following illustration shows how the method schedules the processes. [4]

Figure 6: GPU Time-slicing method

Configuration involved specifying the parameters in a ConfigMap, such as how many replicas should be shown and modifying the GPU device plugin to implement the method based on the ConfigMap. This approach enabled multiple users to run GPU-accelerated workloads in parallel, thereby improving utilization without requiring specialized hardware.

The adoption of time-slicing provided a practical compromise: while not offering the strong isolation guarantees of MIG, it delivered an effective and efficient means of GPU sharing within the constraints of the existing infrastructure.

4 SUMMARY

The implementation of Kubeflow in the LHCb computing environment resulted in a functional and secure MLOps platform capable of supporting machine learning workflows under the constraints of a private network. The deployment successfully addressed the main technical challenges identified at the start of the project, and the following outcomes were achieved:

- Private network deployment: Kubeflow was installed and made fully operational without reliance on external internet access, using mirrored container images and locally hosted manifests.
- Secure multi-user authentication: Integration of Dex with the internal LDAP service enabled users to log in with existing credentials, ensuring compliance with the infrastructure's security model.
- Administrative access: A dedicated administrative user was configured with full privileges across namespaces, supported by a script that ensured consistency between Kubernetes permissions and the Kubeflow user interface.
- GPU sharing: Time-slicing was successfully configured, allowing multiple users to share GPU resources concurrently, significantly improving utilization in comparison to exclusive allocation.

The resulting setup provides a unified environment for data scientists and engineers to develop, train, and deploy machine learning models, while maintaining security, scalability, and efficient resource use. For the LHCb monitoring system, this infrastructure represents a significant step towards integrating advanced machine learning methods into operational workflows, with the potential to improve anomaly detection, predictive analysis, and overall observability.

5 FUTURE STEPS

While the current deployment of Kubeflow establishes a solid foundation for machine learning operations within the LHCb environment, several enhancements remain to be implemented in order to fully exploit its capabilities. The following areas have been identified as the next steps:

- **Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment (CI/CD):**
Integration of CI/CD pipelines will enable automated testing, validation, and deployment of machine learning models. This will reduce manual intervention, improve reproducibility, and shorten the development cycle from prototyping to production.
- **Monitoring and Observability:**
Extending the monitoring stack to cover machine learning workflows will provide greater transparency into system and model performance. Integration with tools such as Prometheus and Grafana will support detailed metrics collection, visualization, and alerting, allowing issues to be detected and resolved proactively.
- **Hyperparameter Optimization with Katib:**
Katib, Kubeflow's automated hyperparameter tuning framework, will be applied to existing machine learning projects within LHCb. This will enable systematic experimentation and optimization, improving model accuracy and efficiency without requiring manual trial-and-error approaches.
- **Advanced GPU Management:**
Although time-slicing currently provides a practical solution for GPU sharing, future improvements could leverage hardware-based partitioning using NVIDIA's Multi-Instance GPU (MIG) technology. The adoption of MIG-capable hardware would provide stronger isolation between workloads and more predictable performance.

These developments will build on the established platform to provide a fully integrated, production-ready MLOps infrastructure, capable of supporting the increasing role of machine learning in LHCb monitoring and operations.

6 CONCLUSION

This project demonstrated the successful deployment and customization of Kubeflow within the LHCb computing environment, addressing the unique constraints of operating in a private, security-restricted infrastructure. The resulting platform enables secure, scalable, and efficient machine learning workflows, providing a foundation for integrating advanced analytics into the monitoring system.

Key achievements include the installation of Kubeflow without external network dependencies, integration with LDAP for user authentication, configuration of administrative access across namespaces, and implementation of GPU sharing through time-slicing. Together, these solutions deliver a functional MLOps framework that aligns with the operational requirements of LHCb while enhancing resource utilization and user accessibility.

The established infrastructure opens the path toward further advancements such as CI/CD integration, enhanced monitoring, automated hyperparameter optimization, and advanced GPU management with MIG-capable hardware. These future developments will extend the platform's capabilities and support the incorporation of machine learning techniques into LHCb's large-scale monitoring workflows.

By providing a robust MLOps environment, this work contributes to improving the efficiency and adaptability of LHCb operations and lays the groundwork for sustained innovation in applying machine learning to high-energy physics computing challenges.

REFERENCES

- [1] *Kubeflow*. URL: <https://www.kubeflow.org/>.
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- [3] *MIG*. URL: <https://www.nvidia.com/en-us/technologies/multi-instance-gpu/>.
- [4] *Time slicing*. URL: <https://docs.nvidia.com/datacenter/cloud-native/gpu-operator/latest/gpu-sharing.html>.

